

ADVANTAGES OF USING THE PROJECT METHOD IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS AS AN EFFECTIVE METHOD OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO STUDENTS OF NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the formation of key communicative competencies and the project method, as one of the interactive methods of teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university. The subject of study in this work is the project method. In this article, the authors note the importance of the project method in the educational process, in working with students of non-linguistic universities. This technology enables the student to experiment, develop creativity and communication skills. The authors reveal the need to use this method in teaching a foreign language in non-linguistic universities, its features and advantages.

Keywords: project method (PM), professional training, communicative competencies, student's active position, creativity, language competence, foreign language in a non-linguistic university.

In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, active forms of learning are widely developed, designed to realize the creative potential of students, namely: the development of erudition, a sense of the new, the ability to introspection, flexibility and breadth of thinking, activity and observation.

One of the most effective in this regard is considered to be the project method (PM), which aims at the emancipation of the student, the elimination of their dependence on the teacher through self-organization and self-learning in the process of creating a specific product or solving a separate problem taken from real life. [1] The project method can be an engaging and motivating way to teach English to students of non-linguistic universities. By designing projects that are relevant and interesting to students, they can be motivated to participate in their learning. For example, students can create a project related to a topic they are interested in, such as music or sports, and use English to research and present their findings. This can help students see the relevance and practical application of the language they are learning, which can lead to greater motivation and engagement.

Also, the use of project-based learning in English lessons of non-linguistic faculties is determined by a number of factors. According to the education modernization strategy, the system for assessing a student's academic achievement is identifying their ability to use the mastered content of education to solve practical-cognitive, value-oriented and communicative tasks and problems. [2] Therefore, students need to master a number of key competencies, in particular, competence in the field of independent cognitive activity, based on

the assimilation of ways to apply knowledge from various sources of information. You should also take into account the level of foreign language proficiency of students of non-linguistic faculties. Based on these factors, the goal was set: as a result of the application of the project method, to achieve active knowledge of English as a means of forming and formulating thoughts in the professional field, as well as to teach students to independently carry out research activities, collect and process material for its subsequent oral and written presentations.

The project method can help students integrate different language skills, such as reading, writing, listening, and speaking, in a meaningful way. By creating projects that require these different language skills, students can develop their language proficiency in a more holistic way. For example, a project that involves interviewing native English speakers or presenting to an audience can help students improve their speaking and listening skills, as well as develop their writing and reading abilities.

The PM can also provide students with authentic language use and exposure, which can help them to develop their communicative competence in English. [3] The project method can encourage collaborative learning, which can help students develop their social and communication skills in English. By working in pairs or groups to complete a project, students can negotiate meaning, practice turn-taking, and give and receive feedback in English. This can help them to advance their language proficiency and their ability to interact with others in English. By designing projects that require students to communicate with native English speakers or create materials for a real-world audience,

students can understand how to use English in real-life situations. This can help them develop their communicative competence and become more confident in their ability to use English.

The project method can be personalized to meet non-linguistic students' individual learning needs and goals. By allowing students to choose a project that aligns with their interests, learning style, or language level, they can feel more invested and engaged in their learning. This can help them develop their language skills in a more meaningful and personalized way. [4]

It should be noted that the use of the project method in a foreign language lesson requires significant preliminary study, because often students do not have presentation skills. Based on the experience of using this method, it would be more expedient to begin the gradual introduction of some aspects of project-based learning, phased familiarization with the PM and development of presentation skills before the implementation of long-term projects.

The project method is also a student-centered teaching approach that can be an effective method of teaching English to students of non-linguistic universities. In this approach, students work on a project that involves investigating, researching, and presenting a topic related to the English language.

There is a significant body of scientific research that supports the use of the project method as an effective method of teaching English to non-linguistic students. Here are some examples of the findings from research studies:

1. Increased Motivation: Research has found that the project method can increase students' motivation to learn English, as it allows them to work on topics that are interesting and relevant to them. [5]

2. Improved Language Proficiency: Several studies have reported that the project method can improve students' language proficiency in various aspects of English, such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing. [6,7]

3. Enhanced Critical Thinking: The project method can also enhance students' critical thinking skills, as it requires them to analyse, synthesize, and evaluate information in order to complete the project. [8]

4. Increased Collaboration: Research has shown that the project method can promote collaboration and teamwork among students, which can help to develop social skills and interpersonal communication. [9]

5. Authentic Assessment: The project method provides opportunities for authentic assessment of students' language skills, as it allows them to demonstrate their language proficiency in a real-world context. [10]

6. Improved Intercultural Communication: The project method can also promote intercultural communication skills, as students can learn about the language, customs, and traditions of different English-speaking countries, and compare and contrast these with their own culture. [11]

Overall, these research findings suggest that the project method is an effective method of teaching English to non-linguistic students. It can enhance students'

motivation, language proficiency, critical thinking, collaboration, assessment, and intercultural communication skills. However, it is important to note that the effectiveness of the project method may depend on factors such as the design of the project, the level of scaffolding and guidance provided by the teacher, and the students' prior knowledge and language proficiency.

The project method is a teaching method that aims to teach students by engaging them in practical and hands-on activities. It is an interactive and participatory approach to teaching that involves students in the process of inquiry and discovery. The project method is a student-centered approach to learning that encourages students to take responsibility for their own learning. [12]

The project method involves the following steps:

1. Identify a project topic: Students select a topic that they are interested in and that is relevant to the course content.

2. Research: Students conduct research on the topic, gathering information from various sources such as books, articles, and the internet.

3. Planning: Students plan the project, developing a timeline, identifying tasks and resources, and setting goals.

4. Implementation: Students carry out the project, using the knowledge and skills they have acquired through research and planning.

5. Presentation: Students present their project to the class, sharing their findings and reflecting on their learning.

Before implementing the project method as an effective method of teaching English to non-linguistic students, there are several preliminary steps that should be taken to ensure that the project is well-designed and meets the needs of the students. Here is some key preliminary work that should be done:

1. Needs Analysis: Before beginning the project, it is important to conduct a needs analysis to determine the English language proficiency and learning needs of the students. This can involve diagnostic assessments, surveys, or interviews with the students and/or their families to determine their language goals and interests.

2. Project Design: Once the needs of the students have been determined, the project should be designed to meet those needs. The project should be based on a topic that is relevant and interesting to the students, and should provide opportunities for authentic language use and real-world application of language skills.

3. Scaffolding: The project should be scaffolded to ensure that the students have the necessary support and guidance to successfully complete the project. This can involve breaking the project into smaller, manageable tasks, providing feedback and guidance throughout the process, and providing resources and materials to support the students' learning.

4. Assessment: The project should be designed with assessment in mind. The teacher should determine how the students will be assessed on their language skills, and should design assessments that are authentic and aligned with the project objectives.

5. Reflection: After the project has been completed, it is important to provide opportunities for the students to reflect on their learning and to provide feedback on the project. This can help to reinforce the learning that has taken place, and can also provide valuable insights for future project design.

By taking these preliminary steps, teachers can ensure that the project method is effectively implemented and meets the learning needs of the non-linguistic students.

Here are some reasons why the project method can be an effective way of teaching English in non-linguistic universities:

1. Active Learning: The project method emphasizes active learning, which means that students are actively involved in their learning process. This approach helps students to understand the language better, as they are not just passive recipients of information but rather active learners who are engaged in their own learning.

2. Relevance: Projects can be designed around topics that are relevant to the students' interests and experiences. This makes the learning more meaningful and motivating for the students, as they can relate to the project content.

3. Collaboration: In the project method, students often work in groups to complete the project. This promotes collaboration and teamwork, which are important skills for students to develop. Working in a group also allows students to learn from one another and share their knowledge and ideas.

4. Problem-solving: Projects often involve solving a problem or answering a question, which requires critical thinking skills. Students are encouraged to analyze and synthesize information to come up with a solution. This helps students to develop their problem-solving and critical thinking skills.

5. Authentic Language Use: The project method can help students to develop their language skills in a more authentic context. Students are exposed to English in real-life situations, which can help them to use the language more confidently and effectively.

6. Multimodal Learning: The project method often involves the use of different media and materials, such as videos, audio recordings, images, and texts. This allows students to engage with English in different ways, and it accommodates different learning styles. Students can also use technology tools and resources to enhance their learning.

7. Student Empowerment: In the project method, students are given more control over their learning process. They have a say in what they learn, how they learn it, and how they demonstrate their learning. This can lead to increased motivation, engagement, and ownership of their learning.

8. Assessment: Projects can provide opportunities for authentic assessment of students' language skills. Teachers can evaluate students' language proficiency based on their ability to communicate, analyze, and present their findings. This type of assessment can provide a more accurate and comprehensive picture of students' language abilities than traditional assessments such as quizzes and tests.

9. Real-World Applications: The project method can be used to teach English for specific purposes, such as business English, academic English, or English for tourism. Students can work on projects that are related to their future careers or interests, which can help them to develop the language skills they need for real-world situations.

10. Cultural Awareness: Projects can also promote cultural awareness and intercultural communication. Students can learn about the language, customs, and traditions of different English-speaking countries, and they can compare and contrast these with their own culture. This can help students to develop a broader perspective and appreciate cultural diversity.

Overall, the project method can be an effective way of teaching English to non-linguistic students. It allows students to engage in active learning, work on relevant topics, collaborate with peers, develop critical thinking skills, and use the language in authentic contexts. It also provides a meaningful, engaging, and authentic learning experience that can help students develop their language skills and communicative competence in English. [13]

One of the latest projects that the 2nd year students of the Faculty of Electricity and Electromechanics of the Vinnytsia National Technical University worked on was a research project "Solar Energy". In terms of the number of participants, it was a pair project, of medium duration, one month was allotted for preparation. After the presentation of their work, the students were asked to answer questions about their motivation, interest in completing assignments, the role of the project in improving their knowledge of the English language, and the ability to work in a group. [14]

The majority of students (75%) noted that the implementation of projects, processing of information and the possibility of obtaining a finished product had a positive impact on the development of creative abilities and improving the level of English proficiency. [15] Students were active participants, listeners, writers, editors. Almost all (89%) of the project participants expressed their desire to continue working on projects and make this form of work traditional.

Thus, it can be argued that this method allows the maximum implementation of the principles of the communicative approach, helps students express their own thoughts, opinions, feelings, while actively engaging in real activities, taking personal responsibility for progress in teaching English and developing their professional competence. During the application of the PM, it was revealed that in addition to reducing the classroom load of the teacher, this method of working with students reduces the number of non-certified students due to their active participation in the work on the project.

Student opinions on the project method of teaching can vary, but there are several common themes that emerge from research studies and unofficial data:

1. Increased Engagement: Many students report that the project method is more engaging and interesting than traditional methods of teaching. Projects can be designed around topics that are relevant to the students' lives or interests, which can help to increase their motivation to learn English.

2. Improved Learning: Students often report that the project method is more effective for learning English than traditional methods. This is because projects provide opportunities for hands-on, experiential learning, which can help to deepen students' understanding and retention of the language.

3. Increased Autonomy: Many students appreciate the increased autonomy and independence that the project method provides. Projects allow students to work at their own pace, and to have more control over their learning process.

4. Improved Interpersonal Skills: The project method often involves collaboration and teamwork, which can help to improve students' interpersonal skills and ability to work in groups.

5. Improved Confidence: Students often report that the project method helps to improve their confidence in using English. This is because projects provide opportunities for authentic language use, which can help to develop students' communication skills.

However, it is important to note that not all students may enjoy or benefit from the project method of teaching. Some students may prefer more structured or traditional methods, and others may find the project method overwhelming or confusing if it is not designed or scaffolded properly. It is important for teachers to consider the needs and preferences of their students, and to be flexible and adaptable in their teaching approach. [16]

Teaching English to non-linguistic students can be a challenging task, but the project method can be an effective way to teach English to these students. By designing projects that are engaging, relevant, and personalized, non-linguistic students can develop their language proficiency in a more holistic and meaningful way. The project method can help non-linguistic students integrate different language skills, provide authentic language use and exposure, encourage collaborative learning, and allow for personalization. [17] By using the project method, teachers can help non-linguistic students develop their language proficiency and become more confident and competent English speakers.

In summary, we may say that the project method is an effective method of teaching English to non-linguistic students because it promotes active learning, relevance, collaboration, problem-solving, authentic language use, multimodal learning, student empowerment, authentic assessment, real-world applications, and cultural awareness.

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HISTORICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE FORMATION OF THE PEDAGOGICAL CULTURE OF SPORTS TEACHER

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Abstract

The foundation of global innovation processes taking place in the system of higher education is the students' motivated assimilation of technologies for obtaining scientific information and the ability to implement their knowledge in professional activities. With this in mind, the educational process in a modern higher education institution is aimed at training a competent specialist, mobile in the labor market, literate and knowledgeable in the field of digital technologies, which have significantly changed the picture of the world and the paradigm of education.

The stage of development at which pedagogical theory and practice is today is characterized by a state of variability, constant dynamics, which requires from the teacher creativity as a normative professional attribute of the individual, and from the student - the ability to effectively and critically process huge masses of information.

The objective logic of the development of the modern socio-cultural and pedagogical situation suggests the need for thorough general pedagogical training. The depth of understanding of the content of professional-pedagogical and general-pedagogical training, in particular, involves changing the external and internal forms of its detection.

Similar processes began in Ukraine in the mid-90s of the 20th century under the influence of a complex set of external factors, primarily the political and socio-economic reorientation of society. The Ukrainian education system is gradually changing its orientation towards integration into the European educational space. This encourages the development of an appropriate strategy, taking into account the peculiarities and achievements of the domestic education system and the search for real opportunities for rapprochement with the European education system.

In the Education Development Concept for 2015-2025, the main direction is to bring the structure of education, which is the subject of public consensus, into compliance with the needs of the modern economy and the integration of Ukraine into the European economic and cultural space.

In the report on the occasion of the 50th anniversary of UNESCO, it is also noted that in the future a decisive role will belong to education that forms the appropriate competences (political, social, intercultural, communicative, informational and technological, the ability to learn throughout life) in its graduates. In the program document of UNESCO «Reform and development of higher education» (1995), it is emphasized: «At the current stage, no country without the training of specialists of the appropriate level... can provide a level of progress that would meet the needs and expectations of society, in which economic development is carried out taking into account the need to provide for the environment and is accompanied by activities to form a «culture of the world» based on principles of democracy, tolerance and mutual respect...» (Bekh, 2005).

The article analyzes the historical and cultural approach to the implementation of the principle of historicism to solve educational and cultural problems. The components that form methodical culture, taking into account innovative ideas and values of the past periods of development of educational thought in Ukraine, are determined. The necessity of connecting the history of pedagogical science with the real problems of the theory and practice of modern pedagogy, in particular the formation of the pedagogical culture of a sports teacher, is proven.

A humanities university, in particular a sports profile, should offer a scheme not only for the assimilation and use of knowledge already in the process of learning and pedagogical practice, but also for their understanding of the unity of general pedagogical disciplines. The need for integrated forms of pedagogical knowledge, its use and problems are caused by the restructuring of higher education to new standards. The idea of dismantling outdated educational standards on the world market and in Ukraine can be implemented through the idea of humanitarian universities.

This idea involves changes to increase the array of general knowledge along with professional knowledge. The integration of knowledge will contribute to the distribution of creative material according to the individual learning trajectories of education seekers, modeled for the purpose of their psychological and pedagogical support as subjects of activity, in particular sports.

The current teacher/trainer has a high level of not only professional, but also general pedagogical training.